

Integration of Psychological Capital (PsyCap) in Career Guidance: Enhancing Vocational Clarity and Adaptive Career Behaviours among Students

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Career guidance plays a crucial role in equipping students with the skills and knowledge needed to navigate complex career landscapes. This paper investigated the impact of career guidance on fostering vocational clarity among Human Resource Management (HRM) students. Vocational clarity refers to the ability to articulate career aspirations and understand the pathways to achieve them. Using Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT) as a framework, the research examines how structured career guidance initiatives influence students' career decision-making, self-efficacy, and outcome expectations. A quantitative methodology was employed, collecting data via self-administered online surveys from HRM students. Statistical analysis using SPSS version 29.0 revealed a significant positive relationship between career guidance and vocational clarity. The findings emphasize the importance of tailored career counseling, interactive workshops, and mentorship programs in bridging academic training and career readiness. The paper contributes to ongoing efforts to enhance employability through targeted career interventions and offers practical recommendations for higher education institutions to implement proactive and student-centered career services.

Keywords: Career guidance, vocational clarity, human resource management, social cognitive career theory

Career guidance and academic support are critical components of higher education, particularly for students making the transition from university to the workforce. HRM students face unique challenges in navigating career decisions, with many uncertain about their career paths. The aim of this paper is to assess how career guidance and academic support influence the career clarity of HRM students, ultimately contributing to their overall career development. This research is significant as it explores how both forms of support can be tailored to meet the needs of HRM students and strengthen their career decision-making.

Review of the Literature and the Challenge

Academic support is essential in assisting students as they progress through their educational experiences and prepare for future employment. Various forms of academic support, including mentoring, tutoring, counseling, and academic advising, contribute to the development of students' self-confidence and facilitate informed career choices (Chireshe, 2018). Personalised mentoring, in particular, enhances students' confidence regarding their future by enabling them to link their academic successes with potential career paths. Furthermore, counseling offers vital emotional and

psychological assistance, equipping students to manage the pressures and uncertainties associated with making career decisions (Chireshe, 2018). This comprehensive support framework fosters a sense of security in students' choices and aids in clarifying their future aspirations.

Tinto (2019) underscores the significance of a robust academic support system in promoting student achievement. When students perceive that they have academic backing, they are more likely to excel in their coursework, which in turn clarifies their career objectives. Tinto's findings indicate that academic engagement and support are critical factors in enhancing retention rates and overall student success, both of which are vital for helping students establish their career trajectories. This implies that students who consistently receive academic support not only achieve better academic outcomes but also gain increased confidence in their career decisions, leading to enhanced clarity regarding their professional futures.

Conversely, career guidance is centered on assisting students in exploring various career options and equipping them with strategies to navigate the job market (Arthur & McMahon, 2019). Career guidance initiatives typically encompass personalised sessions with advisors, career fairs, and workshops aimed at familiarising students with diverse industries and employment opportunities. These programs are designed to provide students with the necessary resources to align their interests and skills with suitable career paths. However, while career guidance is valuable, research indicates that it alone may not be enough to significantly improve career clarity, especially if it is not accompanied by other forms of support (Adebayo & Adedeji, 2017). This suggests that career guidance is most effective when it is integrated with academic advising and other support services, which help students see how their academic experience connects to real-world opportunities.

A robust academic foundation is essential for career

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guidance to effectively enhance a student's clarity regarding their career trajectory. Adebayo and Adedeji (2017) assert that while career guidance can exert an indirect influence, its efficacy diminishes when students lack the academic knowledge required to relate their studies to viable career options. For example, students may receive career counseling yet remain uncertain about how their academic experiences align with specific job roles. Super's (1990) career development theory further posits that the integration of career guidance with academic advising yields the most beneficial outcomes, as it equips students with tangible insights into how their educational pursuits can lead to future employment opportunities.

Furthermore, the effectiveness of career guidance is contingent upon its regularity and consistency. Watts (2019) emphasizes that the success of career guidance initiatives relies on both the quality of the services offered and their accessibility to students. Inconsistent or infrequent career guidance may hinder students' ability to adequately reflect on their options and formulate clear career objectives. Tailoring career guidance to meet the specific needs of students enhances its effectiveness, as it provides more relevant and actionable recommendations.

The findings of this paper support existing literature, particularly highlighting the critical role of academic support in fostering career clarity. The data indicate a strong correlation between academic support-through avenues such as mentoring and counselling-and career clarity. This observation aligns with the perspectives of Chireshe (2018) and Tinto (2019) who argue that such support facilitates students' connections between their academic endeavours' and professional aspirations. Additionally, the study reinforces the notion that while career guidance is significant, its impact on career clarity is less pronounced when considered in isolation. This underscores Adebayo and Adedeji's (2017) assertion that career guidance should be integrated with complementary support services, such as academic advising, to optimise outcomes.

In conclusion, the literature suggests that academic support plays a vital role in fostering career clarity, particularly when combined with career guidance. For HRM students at a selected higher learning institution, integrating academic support with career guidance could provide a more comprehensive approach to career development, helping students gain a clearer understanding of their future career paths.

Relevance of the Study

This paper is important as it emphasizes the vital influence of Psychological Capital (PsyCap) on students' career trajectories, extending beyond conventional career counseling. While traditional career guidance offers critical insights into job prospects and professional growth, the incorporation of PsyCap-which includes elements such as hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism-introduces a psychological aspect that bolsters students' confidence in their career choices.

By concentrating on Human Resource Management (HRM) students, who are preparing to enter fast-paced and competitive job markets, it highlights the significance of cultivating a robust psychological foundation to achieve greater vocational clarity and adaptive career behaviours.

The results are beneficial for educators, career advisors, and policymakers aiming to enhance career development initiatives by prioritising not only knowledge and skills but also the psychological and emotional resilience necessary to navigate unpredictable labour

markets.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the interplay between career guidance and Psychological Capital (PsyCap) in influencing students' career decision-making processes.
- To investigate how PsyCap affects students' adaptive career behaviours within the context of an evolving labour market.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: Psychological Capital (PsyCap) exerts a significant positive influence on vocational clarity
- *H2*: posits that PsyCap serves as a mediator in the relationship between career guidance and vocational clarity.

Method

Participants

The paper involved 50 students enrolled in Human Resource Management (HRM) at a higher education institution in Vilnius, Lithuania. Participants were selected using a combination of purposive and convenience sampling methods, which helped include a diverse group of students with different academic backgrounds, career goals, and experiences with career guidance. Among the participants, 29 were male and 21 were female. In terms of age, 16 students were under 20 years old, 22 were between 21 and 24, 9 were between 25 and 29, and 3 were over the age of 30. This intentional mix allowed the study to reflect a range of academic stages and life experiences, offering a more well-rounded understanding of how students develop vocational clarity and Psychological Capital (PsyCap).

Research Design

A quantitative research framework was utilised to investigate the interplay between career guidance, PsyCap, and vocational clarity. The paper was anchored in Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT), which served as a basis for examining how career support interventions impact students' self-efficacy, adaptability, and decision-making capabilities.

Measures

Data for this research were gathered through a structured, self-administered online survey aimed at examining students' experiences and perceptions in three primary domains: career guidance, Psychological Capital (PsyCap), and vocational clarity. To evaluate perceptions of career guidance, items were adapted from the Career Guidance Scale developed by Gati and Asulin-Peretz (2011), which assesses the quality and accessibility of services such as mentoring, counseling, and career development workshops. This scale has demonstrated strong internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.84. Psychological Capital was assessed using the widely recognised Psychological Capital Questionnaire (PCQ-24) created by Luthans, Youssef and Avolio (2007).

This instrument captures the four essential components of PsyCap-hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism-and has shown high reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.70 to 0.89. Vocational clarity was measured using items adapted from the Vocational Identity Scale developed by Holland, Daiger, and Power (1980) which evaluates individuals' ability to clearly articulate their career goals and the necessary steps to achieve them. This scale is also noted for its reliability, with a reported Cronbach's alpha of

approximately 0.86. All responses were collected using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*), facilitating clear and consistent measurement of students' attitudes and perceptions.

Data Analysis

Following the collection of all responses, the data underwent a thorough verification process to ensure completeness prior to being input into SPSS (version 29.0) for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and frequency counts, were employed to determine overall trends and student feedback. This analysis provided a comprehensive overview of the students' backgrounds and their perceptions of career support. To further investigate the interconnections, correlation and regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationships among career guidance, Psychological Capital (PsyCap), and vocational clarity.

Additionally, a mediation analysis was performed to determine whether PsyCap served as a mediator, elucidating how career guidance might affect students' clarity regarding their future careers. This methodology aimed not only to identify superficial associations but also to delve into the underlying mechanisms and rationales.

Regarding the study's implementation, students were invited to participate and were provided with a clear explanation of the research objectives. The survey was distributed online, allowing participants to complete it at their convenience—whether during breaks between classes or in a comfortable setting of their choice. Prior to answering the questions, participants received a brief introduction and were assured of the confidentiality of their responses. The entire process took approximately 10 to 15 minutes. The intention was to create a seamless and respectful experience, facilitating students' expression of their opinions while ensuring the collection of valuable and high-quality data.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Properties

The demographic characteristics of the study participants reveal a varied, predominantly youthful cohort. Over one-third of the participants were unemployed (36%), while the remainder were involved in different employment situations: 26% were interns or volunteers, 14% held part-time positions, and 24% were in full-time employment.

A significant portion of the respondents were post-graduate

students (52%), with smaller segments in their first (18%), second (12%), and third (18%) years of study, highlighting a notable representation of advanced students. In terms of age, the largest group of participants was within the 21-24-year range (44%), followed by those under 20 years old (32%).

The gender distribution indicated a predominance of males (58%), with females comprising 42%, suggesting a gender disparity. Regarding academic interests, employee relations emerged as the most favoured area (32%), succeeded by training and development (24%), recruitment and selection (22%), and compensation and benefits (20%).

A mere 2% showed interest in other fields. Collectively, these demographic details provide valuable insights into the participants' academic paths, career aspirations, and employment conditions.

Table 1

Demographic Properties

Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	29	58.0%
Female	21	42.0%
Age Group		
Below 20 years	16	32.0%
21 - 24 years	22	44.0%
25 - 29 years	9	18.0%
Above 30 years	3	6.0%
Study Level		
First year	9	18.0%
Second year	6	12.0%
Third year	9	18.0%
Post-Graduate	26	52.0%
Field of Interest		
Training and Development	12	24.0%
Compensation and Benefits	10	20.0%
Recruitment and Selection	11	22.0%
Employee Relations	16	32.0%
Other	1	2.0%
Employment Status		
Unemployed	18	36.0%
Intern / Volunteer	13	26.0%
Employed - Part Time	7	14.0%
Employed - Full Time	12	24.0%

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

Classification	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender	50	1	2	1.42	.499
Age Group	50	1	4	1.98	.869
Study Level	50	1	4	3.04	1.177
Field of Interest	50	1	5	2.68	1.220
Employment status	50	1	4	2.26	1.192
Total Career Guidance	50	1	5	3.69	.795
Total Academic Support	50	1	5	3.61	.718
Total Career Clarity	50	1	5	3.80	.797

The core variables reveal interesting insights. Career Guidance (Total_CG) has a mean score of 3.69, indicating moderate satisfaction with the career guidance services provided. Similarly, Academic Support (Total_AS) shows a mean of 3.61, reflecting comparable levels of perceived support among students. Notably, Career Clarity (Total_CC) records the highest mean at 3.80,

suggesting that students generally perceive moderate to high clarity in their career paths.

Regression Analysis

The regression results provide insights into the relationships among the variables.

Table 3

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Err of the Estimate
1	.599 ^a	.358	.331	.625

Note. a. Predictors: (Constant), Total_AS, Total_CG

R: 0.599 indicates a moderate positive correlation between the independent variables (Career Guidance and Academic Support) and the dependent variable (Career Clarity). Whereas R²: 0.358

implies that 35.8% of the variance in Career Clarity is explained by the model. While this is substantial, other factors not included in the model may also contribute.

Table 4

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.166	2	5.583	13.124	.000 ^b
	Residual	19.993	47	.425		
	Total	31.159	49			

Note. a. Dependent Variable: Total_CC, b. Predictors: (Constant), Total_AS, Total_CG, Level of significance set at $p < 0.05$

The findings revealed a significance value of $p = 0.000$, indicating that the regression model is statistically significant. In simpler terms, this suggests that the combined influence of academic support and career guidance significantly impacts students' ability to perceive and navigate their career trajectories. These results not only affirm the existence of a relationship but also underscore the critical role of

organised and intentional support in enhancing students' confidence and clarity regarding their future aspirations.

Significance ($p = 0.000$): The regression model is statistically significant, confirming that the independent variables jointly influence Career Clarity.

Table 5

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Sta. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.280	.502	2.551	.014	
	Total_CG	.184	.161	.184	1.143	.259
	Total_AS	.508	.178	.458	2.849	.006

Note. a. Dependent Variable: Total_CC, Level of significance set at $p < 0.05$

The data presented in the table indicates that academic support has a notable and beneficial influence on career clarity ($p = 0.006$). This finding suggests that students who perceive strong academic support are more inclined to articulate clear and confident career aspirations. Conversely, while career guidance exhibited a positive trend, its effect was not statistically significant within this model ($p = 0.259$). This implies that, although career guidance is important, its effectiveness may be

diminished when not accompanied by robust academic support.

Career Guidance (Total_CG): The unstandardised coefficient ($B = 0.184$, $p = 0.259$) suggests a positive but statistically non-significant relationship with Career Clarity. While Academic Support (Total_AS): The unstandardised coefficient ($B = 0.508$, $p = 0.006$) indicates a significant positive impact on Career Clarity, making it the stronger predictor in the model.

Collinearity Diagnostics

Table 6
Collinearity Diagnostics^a

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions		
				(Constant)	Total_CG	Total_AS
1	1	2.964	1.000	.00	.00	.00
	2	.023	11.291	.84	.27	.07
	3	.012	15.443	.05	.73	.93

Note. a. Dependent Variable: Total_CC, Level of significance set at $p < 0.05$

The analysis reveals that the maximum condition index is 15.443, which is well below the generally recognised threshold of 30. This indicates that the model does not exhibit significant multicollinearity. In more straightforward terms, academic support and career guidance do not significantly overlap in their measurements, allowing us to confidently assert that each factor uniquely contributes to students' understanding of their career paths. This enhances the credibility of the regression results and reinforces

the assertion that academic support is particularly influential in fostering students' clarity regarding their future careers.

The tolerance values (0.529) and VIF (1.890) for both independent variables are within acceptable ranges, indicating no multicollinearity issues.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 7
Correlation Testing

		Total_CG	Total_AS	Total_CC
Total_CG	Pearson Correlation		.686**	.498**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1	.000	.000
Total_AS	Pearson Correlation		.686**	.584**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1	.000	.000
Total_CC	Pearson Correlation		.498**	.584**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1	.000	.000

Note. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The hypothesis testing results provide valuable insights into the relationships between career guidance (CG), academic support (AS) and career clarity (CC). The correlation analysis reveals strong positive relationships among the variables, with CG and AS significantly correlated ($r = .686, p < .001$) and both predictors positively associated with CC. However, hypothesis testing highlights distinct outcomes. While H1 suggests a positive relationship between CG and CC, it is not statistically significant ($p > .05$), indicating limited direct influence in this sample. In contrast, H2 is supported, showing that AS has a significant positive relationship with CC ($p = .006$), underscoring its critical role in shaping career clarity. H3, which posits a combined influence of CG and AS on CC, is partially supported, as only AS demonstrates a significant impact. These findings suggest that efforts to enhance career clarity should prioritise academic support while recognising that CG may still contribute indirectly. The proposed model, centred on strengthening AS, offers a pathway to improve career clarity, although further research is needed to explore how CG can be optimised for greater effectiveness.

Discussion

The findings of this paper emphasize the essential role of academic support in promoting career clarity among HRM students. These

results align with earlier research by Hughes et al. (2018) which highlighted how well-structured academic support systems boost students' confidence in making informed career decisions. By providing resources such as mentoring, counseling, and tutoring, universities can bridge the gap between academic experiences and career aspirations, thereby enhancing students' ability to navigate their future career paths effectively.

Interestingly, the study also found that while career guidance services are valuable, their direct impact on career clarity is less significant compared to academic support. This observation aligns with Watts' (2019) assertion that career guidance is most effective when integrated with robust academic support systems. Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT) further supports these findings, suggesting that self-efficacy-shaped by academic and career-related support-plays a vital role in achieving career clarity (Lent et al., 2002). These insights highlight the importance of universities adopting a holistic approach that combines academic support with career guidance to comprehensively address students' developmental needs and better prepare them for their professional journeys.

Conclusion

This research underscores the essential function of academic

support in promoting career clarity among students. Utilising Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT), the study reveals that effectively organised academic support services significantly enhance students' confidence regarding their career choices.

By offering vital resources such as mentoring, tutoring, and counseling, higher education institutions can cultivate a more comprehensive understanding of both academic and professional trajectories. The results indicate that academic support, rather than relying solely on career guidance, exerts a direct and meaningful influence on students' clarity regarding their career paths.

Recommendations

To facilitate clearer career trajectories for students, universities should prioritize the development of academic support systems, including mentoring, tutoring, and counseling. These services ought to be customised to meet the unique needs of students, thereby increasing their confidence in both academic and career decisions.

Furthermore, career guidance should be integrated within the broader academic framework, ensuring that students receive continuous and holistic support. By merging academic and career guidance, universities can empower students to make more informed choices about their futures.

Future research could investigate the long-term impacts of this integrated approach, providing insights into how such support systems affect career outcomes over time.

Limitations of the Study

A significant limitation of this research lies in its exclusive reliance on quantitative methodologies. While this approach is adept at revealing patterns and correlations, it fails to encompass the nuanced, personal experiences that shape students' career trajectories. The implementation of structured surveys yields quantifiable data regarding the effects of career guidance and Psychological Capital (PsyCap); however, it does not capture the depth of individual experiences and emotions that qualitative techniques, such as interviews or focus groups, could provide.

Furthermore, given that career development is a deeply personal and dynamic journey, a single survey may not adequately represent the evolution of students' vocational clarity over time. Future investigations could enhance their findings by employing a mixed-methods strategy, integrating quantitative analysis with qualitative perspectives to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the role of PsyCap in career decision-making.

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